

Supplementary Figure 2

Histopathological findings of multifocal tumors and an adrenal medullary hyperplasia from Case 3

* Hematoxylin and eosin (HE) staining and immunohistochemistry for chromogranin A (CgA) of a pheochromocytoma (PCC), an adrenal medullary hyperplasia (AMH) and a microscopic bladder paraganglioma (PGL) from Case 3. AMH represents a substantial widening of the adrenal medulla, indicated by a blue arrowhead. Tumor and AMH cells showed positive chromogranin A staining.